

The battle for trust:

Advancing the social science data ecosystem

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Authors' note

The authors have developed this brief as part of the CESSDA Trust and Landscape Working Group. The authors would like to acknowledge the contributors of CESSDA colleagues in contributing their expert knowledge through several rounds of review, including Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch (CESSDA ERIC), Maaïke Verburg (Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)), Hervé L'Hours (UK Data Service (UKDS)), Ami Saji (Progedo), and Morten Jakobsen (Sikt).

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15125538

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Published in April 2025

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Full term
AI	Artificial intelligence
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
CDC	CESSDA Data Catalogue
CESSDA	Consortium for European Social Science Data Archives
COAR	Confederations of Open Access Repositories
DDI	Discover, Document, and Interoperate
DDI-CDI	DDI Cross-Domain Integration
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Life	European Open Science Cloud-Life
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESCAPE	European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
MAR	Multi-Annual Roadmap
NDSA	National Digital Steward Alliance
ODC	Open Data Charter
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society
PaNOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud
PID	Persistent identifiers
RACER	Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor, and Robust
RDA	Research Data Alliance

Abbreviation	Full term
SP	Service Provider
SPARC Europe	Scholarly Publishing Academic Resources Coalition Europe
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSHOC	Social Science & Humanities Open Cloud
STREAM	Sovereign, Trusted, Reusable, Exchangeable, Actionable, and Measurable
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
TRSP	Technical Repository Service Provider
TRSPs WG	Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, Technology
WDS	World Data System

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Introduction

This brief presents an overview of the current landscape in open data from the perspective of European social science data archives.¹ It focuses on key topics such as community principles (FAIR, TRUST, and CARE), trustworthy digital repositories, ongoing European and international initiatives, and performance assessments. It leverages insights gathered through several years of monitoring and various collaborative activities by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) Trust and Landscape Working Group (Dolinar *et al.*, 2022; Kvamme *et al.*, 2022; Braukmann *et al.*, 2023).

This brief aims to inform practices in the data archiving community and a broader audience in the context of a rapidly evolving open data ecosystem. While technological developments are foundational to data repositories' work, they fall outside the scope of this brief.

By presenting these findings and key takeaways, CESSDA aims to contribute to the ongoing discussions on FAIR and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) matters. CESSDA also aims to support social science data archives in improving practices, fostering collaboration, and enhancing contributions to the research community.

The evolving landscape of open data

The evolving landscape of open data in social science is characterised by a shifting paradigm – from closed, restricted datasets to open, accessible data – that fosters transparency and collaboration (Paic, 2021). The Horizon Europe programme guidelines further specify that data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary (European Commission, 2024a). The transition is largely motivated by data-driven innovation, rapid advancements in data infrastructures, and increasing mandates from governments and funding agencies (Paic, 2021; Digital Science *et al.*, 2023). At the core of this shift are the community principles of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology), and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics), which guide responsible data sharing and governance. While these community principles traditionally promote openness, they often assume that open data are inherently beneficial (Batzdorfer *et al.*, 2024). However, as open data become more prominent, maintaining the balance between data accessibility and privacy protection presents new challenges, particularly in the ethical handling of sensitive data, compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the emerging role of artificial intelligence (AI) in data governance (European Union, 2024).

Recognising the growing interest in open data, recent studies have assessed the societal value of open data. In the context of citizen science, Cole *et al.* (2024) find that engaging diverse

¹ The terms "data archives" and "data repositories" are used interchangeably in this brief.

communities in research yields broad societal benefits. However, more research is needed to measure the impact of open data, FAIR data, open-source tools, and open-access publications. Based on survey results on open science practices in social sciences, Ferguson et al. (2023) highlight that while most researchers support open science, they often underestimate its adoption in their field. In a separate survey, Digital Science et al. (2023) report that while publishing research data boosts trust and citations, researchers often receive insufficient credit for sharing their data.

From the measurement perspective, de Bas and Page (2024) identify indicators – including those with the potential for automation – for measuring the impact of open data, but the testing and implementation of these indicators require cooperation across the open data value chain, time, and resources. In line with the indicator framework of de Bas and Page (2024), Hemphill et al. (2024) published a dataset with information on factors contributing to long-term data reuse, so that data users (including researchers, publishers, data archives, and policy actors) can make evidence-based decisions in leveraging data reuse.

Beyond measuring societal value, sustaining open data and open science practices requires long-term investments in preservation and curation. Parr et al. (2019) emphasise that funding for data repositories is critical for supporting future science and addressing societal needs. Taken together, these recent studies highlight the need to develop better metrics and incentives to measure the societal impact of data archives and ensure researchers' long-term support for open science practices. They underscore the importance of engaging the research community to leverage the full potential of research infrastructures and data archives.

Guiding principles for data management and stewardship

As the landscape of social science data archiving continues to evolve, shared principles play a critical role in guiding best practices and fostering trust within the community. This brief highlights three community principles that underpin effective data management and stewardship: FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology), and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics). Together, these principles provide a comprehensive framework for ensuring data quality, accessibility, and ethical stewardship, while reflecting technical- and community-centred priorities.

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

The FAIR principles emphasise that data should be *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable* (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). According to Wilkinson *et al.* (2016), *Findable* refers to easy-to-find metadata (data describing data) and data for machines and humans, involving a globally unique and persistent identifier. *Accessible* means metadata and data are retrievable via a standardised communications protocol, even when the data are no longer available. *Interoperable* indicates that metadata and data are machine-readable such that information can be accessed and shared across applications or workflows. Finally, *Reusable* necessitates that metadata and data are well-described and associated with clear provenance.

The implementation of the FAIR principles presents three main challenges, along with potential solutions to address them. First, the principles do not consider the long-term sustainability of FAIR data. The principles do not account for time-varying changes in user needs, data environments, and technology. Keeping data FAIR over time requires continuous preservation efforts. For instance, L'Hours *et al.* (2022) emphasise the importance of defining a designated community of users in the "FAIR + TIME" framework. Second, interoperability is difficult to achieve as different disciplines and repositories use varying metadata standards and formats (Corcho *et al.*, 2021; Kalinin and Skvortsov, 2023). To address this challenge, standardised ontologies and improved multi-disciplinary research collaboration would be essential ([Box 1](#) on the next page summarises the role of metadata standards).

Third, the effectiveness of FAIR initiatives remains a concern (van Reisen *et al.*, 2020). Reisen *et al.* (2020) assessed over 1,500 articles which cited Wilkinson *et al.* (2016) – the original article on the FAIR principles – that were published between 2016 and 2019. They find that FAIR principles are mainly implemented in Europe, particularly in bio-science and natural sciences. As such, broader coordination across scientific disciplines and geographic regions is needed to ensure more inclusive implementation of the FAIR principles. Moreover, increased coordination among data managers, university librarians, and discipline-specific repositories, such as CESSDA Service Providers (SPs), can help streamline FAIR data management and provide researchers with more practical support.

To translate the FAIR principles into action, manual approaches and automated tools have been developed to quantify FAIRness (further discussed in the section, FAIR assessments). Some automated tools include the F-UJI assessment tool (Devaraju *et al.*, 2021), the FAIR-Checker (Gaignard *et al.*, 2023), the FAIR Evaluation Services (FAIRsharing, 2018), and the FAIR Enough metrics (Maastricht University, 2020). Furthermore, there is growing interest in extending the FAIR principles beyond metadata and data to include other digital objects (e.g., semantic resources, ontologies, and software) (Vogt *et al.*, 2024). Expanding the FAIR principles and developing clear guidelines for these digital objects would help integrate them into the FAIR ecosystem effectively.

◆ **Box 1: The role of metadata standards**

Standardised, high-quality metadata is key to FAIRness. The use of standardised metadata and persistent identifiers is fundamental to the discovery and reuse of repository resources. A joint strategy by four library-based open science communities (OpenAIRE, LIBER, SPARC Europe, and COAR) identified three key areas that need to be strengthened to ensure the European repository network is fit for purpose (Shearer *et al.*, 2023). One of the key areas is the application of consistent and comprehensive practices on metadata, preservation, and usage statistics.²

Dublin Core metadata is supported by most repositories; it is considered the baseline for interoperability across repositories in Europe (Shearer *et al.*, 2023). Another widely adopted metadata standard is the OpenAIRE guidelines; they require additional metadata elements and are more granular.

In social sciences, the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) is a widely used metadata standard. Recent DDI developments include the review of the second beta version of DDI Lifecycle 4.0 and the approval of DDI Cross-Domain Integration (DDI-CDI) version 1.0 (DDI, 2024a, 2024b). DDI-CDI extends traditional DDI metadata to describe data beyond the social sciences. It is designed to work with controlled vocabularies from any domain and other standards (DDI, 2025).

All in all, the latest development in metadata standards reaffirms that the adoption of high-quality, consistent metadata standards across disciplines and repositories is essential for maximising data interoperability, discovery, and reuse.

TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, Technology)

The TRUST principles aim to demonstrate the trustworthiness of digital repositories through *Transparency*, *Responsibility*, *User Focus*, *Sustainability*, and *Technology* (Lin *et al.*, 2020). *Transparency* stresses that repository services and data holdings are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence. *Responsibility* emphasises ethical stewardship – where data are curated and shared in compliance with legal, ethical, and professional standards. *User Focus* prioritises the needs of target user communities. *Sustainability* addresses long-term data preservation and infrastructure maintenance. Finally, *Technology* supports secure and efficient data management through robust security measures and data standards.³ The principles inform

² The other two areas are maintaining up-to-date, highly functioning software platforms; and enhancing visibility in the scholarly system (Shearer *et al.*, 2023).

³ In trustworthy repositories, data standards encompass metadata schema, data file formats, controlled vocabularies, ontologies, and other semantics that exist in the user community (Lin *et al.*, 2020).

the discussion and implementation of best practices in digital preservation by all stakeholders, including data users, funders, and journal editors. The principles have been endorsed by over 40 organisations, including several CESSDA SPs (RDA, 2020).

The implementation of the TRUST principles comes with three main challenges (see also a related discussion on the implementation of data sovereignty (Hellmeier *et al.*, 2023)). First, ensuring openness while protecting data subjects in sensitive data and complying with diverse legal and ethical frameworks can be complex. Second, the sustainability of data archives and long-term digital preservation relies on financial, human, and technical resources. Stable funding, institutional support, and long-term preservation strategies are needed, but they are not guaranteed in practice. Third, addressing diverse user requirements, ensuring accessibility, and managing evolving technological standards across domain-specific repositories can be challenging.

To overcome these challenges, collaborative efforts among data stewards, researchers, and policymakers are needed to develop and implement sustainable, user-centred, and technologically robust data archiving solutions.

CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics)

The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (*Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics*) aim to ensure that Indigenous communities have agency over their data while promoting ethical and equitable data stewardship in social science research (Carroll *et al.*, 2020). The CARE principles complement mainstream principles, such as FAIR (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016), Open Data Charter (ODC) Principles (ODC, 2015), and STREAM Properties for Industrial and Commoditized Data (Demchenko, Los and de Laat, 2018), with people- and purpose-oriented approaches to data governance.⁴ *Collective Benefit* highlights that data should support Indigenous people to achieve inclusive development and innovation rather than just academic or institutional interests. *Authority to Control* affirms Indigenous people's rights and interests in their data. *Responsibility* refers to the duty of data stewards to respect Indigenous data sovereignty, invest in capacity development, and engage in meaningful collaboration with Indigenous communities. Finally, *Ethics* requires that data practices align with community values and cultural contexts throughout data lifecycles to minimise harm, maximise benefits, promote justice, and encourage future use. The CARE principles foster trust, support ethical research collaborations, and ensure that indigenous data are properly managed.

⁴ The STREAM properties for industrial and commoditized data are Sovereign, Trusted, Reusable, Exchangeable, Actionable, and Measurable (Demchenko, Los and de Laat, 2018).

Despite their importance, Carroll et al. (2021) described two main challenges in operationalising CARE and presented synergies between the FAIR and CARE principles. First, aligning the widely adopted FAIR principles and CARE principles can be difficult; FAIR focuses on data characteristics, whereas CARE emphasises the rights and interests of indigenous communities. Therefore, the authors suggest developing frameworks to harmonise FAIR and CARE. This includes developing criteria for cultural metadata, provenance, and Indigenous governance and ethics.

Second, many Indigenous communities lack the technological infrastructure and funding to operationalise CARE (Carroll *et al.*, 2021). This hinders the ability of Indigenous people to manage and govern their data effectively. Thus, capacity building, technical infrastructure development, and CARE criteria and tools are needed to enable Indigenous data sovereignty. This means that Indigenous data and metadata should be well-documented and compliant with the FAIR principles while using protocols that align with community values. Similar to the FAIR Data Maturity Model criteria, a clear set of CARE criteria and assessment tools can be developed through consultations to support the implementation of CARE.

Looking forward, there is increasing interest in applying the CARE principles beyond indigenous communities (Carroll *et al.*, 2020, 2021). Particularly relevant to the European context, CARE could serve as a model to advance data governance practices for communities with collective rights, such as workers, people with diverse sexual orientations, gender identities and expressions, and sex characteristics (SOGIESC), and marginalised and vulnerable groups, including refugees and persons with disabilities.

Overlapping concepts among FAIR, TRUST, and CARE

In summary, the community principles of FAIR, TRUST, and CARE provide complementary frameworks for advancing the open data landscape. While FAIR focuses on making data more discoverable and reusable, TRUST emphasises building trustworthy digital repositories through responsible stewardship, sustainability, and user-oriented design. On the other hand, CARE prioritises inclusive access, ethical data governance through capacity building, and respect for data subjects, particularly marginalised communities. These principles intersect in their shared commitment to an ethical, sustainable, and transparent data ecosystem (see a conceptual illustration in [Figure 1](#) below).

◆ **Figure 1: A conceptual illustration of the overlapping themes across FAIR, TRUST, and CARE**

Source: Authors' illustration.

FAIR and TRUST overlap in Findability (FAIR) and Transparency (TRUST) to highlight the importance of data provenance and standardised metadata. Interoperability (FAIR) and Technology (TRUST) advocate robust infrastructure, while Reusability (FAIR) and Sustainability (TRUST) encourage long-term data reuse through proper documentation and governance.

FAIR and CARE overlap in Accessibility (FAIR) and Collective Benefit (CARE) by ensuring data serves as a public good through training. Interoperability (FAIR) and Authority to Control (CARE) highlight respecting data subjects' rights while enabling data reuse. Moreover, Reusability (FAIR) and Ethics (CARE) ensure ethical principles guide the data lifecycle.

TRUST and CARE overlap in Responsibility (TRUST and CARE) with a shared commitment to ethical data stewardship. User Focus (TRUST) and Authority to Control (CARE) ensure communities have agency over their data. Finally, Sustainability (TRUST) and Collective Benefit (CARE) advocate for long-term data use that benefits society.

These principles reinforce the need for social science data archives to ensure openness and interoperability, without compromising privacy, ethical integrity, and responsible data use.

Trustworthy digital repositories and CoreTrustSeal certification

Scholarly research activities, such as discovering data and referring to relevant literature, are generally well-supported by data archives. However, this does not offer proof that the repository's data or features are managed and operated in a trustworthy and reliable manner (Kleemola *et al.*, 2020). With an agreed set of standards and criteria, the sustainability and reliability of data repositories can be assessed. Moreover, funding agencies increasingly require data produced by their projects to remain useful and meaningful in the future. Formal certification addresses this need and guarantees that the data and services offered by repositories meet the quality standards as outlined in the predefined criteria.

Trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs) are those that provide digital preservation services and meet predefined criteria for organisational infrastructure, digital object management, technology, and security requirements (Anglada *et al.*, 2024). They support long-term digital preservation and FAIR data. For instance, the National Digital Steward Alliance (NDSA) provides the Levels of Digital Preservation framework to assess digital preservation practices (NDSA, 2019). However, it does not grant a formal certification.

In contrast to the NDSA Levels of Digital Preservation, CoreTrustSeal is a certification that formally recognises repositories meeting established criteria for trustworthiness. While the NDSA Levels help guide best practices, data repositories seeking official recognition of trustworthiness would pursue certifications such as CoreTrustSeal, [nestor-Seal DIN 31644](#), or [ISO16363](#).

The CoreTrustSeal certification is considered the first step in the global repository certification framework (CoreTrustSeal 2024). As of 31 October 2024, 144 repositories have achieved CoreTrustSeal certification, while 5 were certified at the extended level (nestor-Seal DIN 31644) and 2 were at the formal level (ISO16363). Moreover, the CoreTrustSeal certification has been the prerequisite for applying for or renewing the WDS regular membership since July 2017 (CoreTrustSeal, 2020). [Box 2](#) introduces CoreTrustSeal.

◆ Box 2: What is CoreTrustSeal?

CoreTrustSeal is an international, community-based, non-governmental, and non-profit organization promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures (CoreTrustSeal 2024). It was launched in 2017 as a cooperative effort between the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) and the World Data System of the International Science Council (WDS), under the umbrella of the Research Data Alliance (RDA), to harmonise their data repository certifications.

CoreTrustSeal is governed by the Standards and Certification Board, which is elected every four years. The Board is responsible for developing and maintaining the certification criteria and processes and approving certifications. In November 2024, elections for the CoreTrustSeal Board were completed. The new Board, serving from 2025 to 2027, includes representatives from CESSDA SPs. It ensures strong connections and relevance to the social science research community.

The CoreTrustSeal certification process includes two steps. First, the repository conducts an internal self-assessment against the 16 requirements (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2022). Then, the application is reviewed by community peers and the CoreTrustSeal Board. The Board defines four preservation levels (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2024):⁵

- **Z. Level zero:** Data and metadata are distributed in the state provided by depositors. There are no checks of deposit compliance, no initial curation, and no active long-term preservation.
- **D. Deposit compliance:** Data and metadata are checked by the repository against the defined criteria. Digital objects that do not comply with these criteria may be rejected or undergo initial curation.
- **C. Initial curation:** Data and metadata are curated by the repository to meet the defined criteria.
- **A. Active preservation:** In addition to levels "D" (check for compliance) and/or "C" (curation), the repository undertakes long-term logical-technical and semantic measures to ensure digital objects can be understood and reused.

To improve curation and preservation practices, metadata standards must evolve to describe and assess preservation levels effectively. L'Hours, Kleemola, and Recker (2024) outline a structured approach to managing digital assets, implementing preservation strategies, and communicating their curation and preservation commitments. Similarly, some practical tools, such as checklists, have been developed to help data curators and preservation staff assess

⁵ A repository may implement different levels of curation and preservation for different digital objects (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2024).

the long-term preservation potential of data deposited in the repository (Knazook, Clary and Narlock, 2024).

Beyond the repository, Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSPs) play an important role in providing tools and services to help achieve CoreTrustSeal certification. TRSPs are software providers and providers of technical infrastructure and associated services (CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board, 2020). As TRSPs are usually third-party service providers, they need to offer transparent information on the functions and activity areas which they support. An example of thorough and detailed documentation is the “Dataverse Software Guide for CoreTrustSeal certification”, which assists repositories in applying for CoreTrustSeal certification (Gautier, 2021). TRSPs should also publish interoperable service catalogues to improve transparency and comparability of services.

As an ongoing effort, the RDA Working Group on Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSPs WG) is working to extend trust frameworks, such as formal certification, to these third-party TRSPs. This effort would be beneficial in strengthening trust across the data management ecosystem.

Certification status of CESSDA Service Providers

Many social science data repositories, including CESSDA SPs, have achieved or are working towards CoreTrustSeal certification. This demonstrates data repositories’ strong commitment to FAIR data and to maintaining reliable data repositories. Most CESSDA SPs operate at “Level A” (Active Preservation), although they may hold digital objects at lower levels of curation and preservation. As of October 2024, about half of the CESSDA SPs have achieved CoreTrustSeal certification.

In a recent analysis of 241 repositories, including several CESSDA SPs, Lazzeri (2024) finds that almost 80% of the sampled repositories (n=186) can be identified as trustworthy. However, there is room for improvement in complying with the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requirements for metadata (Jahn *et al.*, 2023; Lazzeri, 2024). This underscores the importance of clear definitions and standardised practices to ensure consistency across repositories.

Fostering community principles through collaboration

The European Open Science Cloud Federation

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation aims to create a trusted and interoperable research environment by connecting EOSC Nodes (European Commission, 2024b). The EOSC Nodes serve as access points for researchers across scientific disciplines and countries. These interconnected Nodes provide essential services, such as computer resources and data management tools, to ensure long-term data retention and adherence to FAIR principles.

At the EOSC Symposium 2024, the launch of the first EOSC EU Node marked a pivotal moment in shaping the European research data landscape (EOSC, 2024a, 2024b). Discussions focused on the governance and sustainability of EOSC, with pilot Nodes set to onboard in 2025 to test funding and operational models. As EOSC and its nodes are being set up, ensuring equitable access to data and services remains a challenge, with national funders considering restrictions on research data as the “new oil”.

The EOSC Federation Handbook is being developed – where CESSDA is part of the core writing team (EOSC, 2025). The Handbook will provide guidelines on governance, structure, architecture, and operations to support collaborations and contributions to EOSC.

Governance, collaboration, and policy alignment at EU and national levels

To encourage collaboration and ensure sustainability, EOSC operates under a Tripartite Governance model involving the European Commission (EC), the EOSC Association, and the Member States and the Associated Countries of the policy sub-group EOSC Steering Board (EOSC, 2022). The governance structure supports the alignment of national and European Union (EU) policies to support open science and increase the quality and accessibility of research data.

EOSC is further supported by [Task Forces](#) and [Opportunity Area Expert Groups](#), which bring together hundreds of expert volunteers, including CESSDA representatives, working on:

- Technical and Semantic Interoperability
- FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects
- Health Data
- Long-Term Data Retention
- Persistent Identifiers
- Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability
- FAIR Assessment and Alignment
- User and Resource Environments
- Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling

- Open Scholarly Communication

Moreover, the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA 1.3) and Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR 2025-2027) outline priorities and future investments for EOSC at the European, national, and institutional levels (EOSC, 2023, 2024c).

Advancing open science through Science Clusters and EU projects

Five [Science Clusters](#), which bring together leading European research infrastructures, are supporting the integration of discipline-specific infrastructure into EOSC (see [Table 1](#)). In 2024, these clusters published a position statement to advocate for adaptable approaches across disciplines and sustainable funding for open science (Petzold *et al.*, 2024). CESSDA contributed to this effort as a key member of the Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) cluster within the social sciences and humanities and as a member of the Science Cluster Steering Board.

Table 1: An overview of the Science Clusters

Scientific domain	Cluster
Astronomy and particle physics	European Science Cluster of Astronomy and Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures (ESCAPE)
Environmental science	ENVRI-hub
Life science	European Open Science Cloud - Life (EOSC-Life)
Photon and neutron science	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud (PaNOSC)
Social sciences and humanities	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)

The project, “Open Science Clusters’ Action for Research & Society” ([OSCARS](#)), further supports the uptake of open science practices by providing cascading grants for researchers not yet exposed to EOSC, a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), or acquainted with open science practices.⁶ OSCARS also creates opportunities for multi-disciplinary research collaboration. Meanwhile, EU-funded initiatives, such as EOSC Gravity, shape the transition of EOSC into a sustainable governance and funding framework.⁷

⁶ The objectives of the OSCARS cascading grants are in line with the [COAR recommendations for supporting the long tail of research data](#).

⁷ EU-funded initiatives include [Horizon Europe](#) projects and those listed under the interactive catalogue, [Macro-Roadmap](#).

CESSDA's contribution to the evolving open data landscape

Through active participation in EU projects, working groups, and international initiatives, CESSDA contributes to the social science data archiving ecosystem in three main ways. First, it strengthens trust in data repositories by building a network of TDRs and identifying best practices for long-term preservation. Second, it advances the implementation of FAIR principles by developing tools and standards. Third, it advocates for open science policy and research infrastructure development. These efforts collectively contribute to a more cohesive, accessible, and trustworthy research data landscape. [Box 3](#) outlines CESSDA's contribution as members or active contributors to these areas.

◆ **Box 3: CESSDA's contribution to the TRUST and FAIR landscape**

Strengthening trust in digital repositories

- The [FIDELIS](#) project aims to build a sustainable European network of Trusted Digital Repositories (TDRs) by fostering a more reliable and interoperable research data infrastructure within EOSC. The project is also exploring ways (in addition to CoreTrustSeal certification) to demonstrate trustworthiness.
- The [CoreTrustSeal Maintenance Working Group](#) within the Research Data Alliance ensures the continued development and updates of trust certification standards.
- Many CESSDA SPs are either members or are actively involved within the Research Data Alliance (RDA). Within the RDA, the [Community-based catalogue of requirements of trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group \(TRSPs WG\)](#) aims to expand the trust framework to data repositories and associated services through formal certification authorities, such as ISO and CoreTrustSeal.

Advancing FAIR principles in data management

- Projects such as [FAIR-IMPACT](#) and [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) focus on improving FAIR-enabling tools, metadata frameworks, and interoperability across repositories. As an example of project outputs, the CESSDA Technical Guidelines for Social Science were mapped to the automated FAIR software assessment metrics to show how other communities can apply these metrics (Hong *et al.*, 2023).
- The [OSTrails](#) project streamlines the FAIRness, interconnectivity, and machine-actionability of research workflows and encourages data reuse.
- The [FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group](#) within the Research Data Alliance establishes standardised criteria for assessing FAIRness to promote consistent data quality measures.

- Repository registries (e.g., [CoreTrustSeal](#), [re3data](#), [OpenDOAR](#), [Fairsharing](#), and [Research Organization Registry](#)) support FAIR principles by making research repositories discoverable and transparent. CESSDA SPs are registered in these repository registries.

Advocating open science policy and research infrastructure development

- The [EOSC EDEN](#) project focuses on long-term data preservation and curation strategies to ensure that high-quality data across scientific disciplines remain reusable and accessible.
- The [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) advocates for transparency in research evaluation and inclusive data.⁸
- Projects such as [PATTERN](#) and [EVERSE](#) aim at improving open and responsible research and innovation practices and creating high-quality research software.⁹
- The [Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions \(RDA TIGER\)](#) project strengthens EOSC partnerships and international engagements by aligning global open science developments with European open science goals.¹⁰

Enhancing transparency and accountability through performance assessment

Effective information collection and performance assessments are critical for enhancing transparency and accountability. Data repositories and research infrastructures should evaluate their processes regularly to identify areas for improvement. By tracking key performance indicators (KPIs) and conducting FAIR assessments, they can strengthen trustworthiness, improve interoperability, and support international initiatives for responsible data archiving.

Key Performance Indicators

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) designates advanced and competitive research infrastructures in the European Research Area as "Landmarks".

⁸ Although CESSDA as a consortium is not a signatory, many CESSDA stakeholders, including EOSC and RDA) are signatories.

⁹ CESSDA and its SPs are not directly involved in the EVERSE project.

¹⁰ One of CESSDA's SP, the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data (DANS) is a partner in this project.

Landmarks undergo regular performance assessments based on the Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor, and Robust (RACER) criteria. In the 2024 ESFRI monitoring cycle, ESFRI and national governments have shifted focus from traditional performance metrics to impact assessments, placing greater emphasis on quantifying the long-term societal benefits of research infrastructures.

As an ESFRI Landmark, CESSDA has established a long-standing practice of collecting performance-related information from its SPs since 2003. Since 2021, it has gathered quantitative key performance indicators (C-KPIs) to align its core activities with the set of ESFRI KPIs to enable a structured evaluation of its impact (CESSDA, 2025). In response to ESFRI's 2024 monitoring recommendations, CESSDA plans to complement its existing quantitative metrics by collecting qualitative impact stories. These narratives will help capture the Consortium's contributions to the research community. This systematic information collection process helps CESSDA strengthen its role as a trusted research infrastructure for social science research (see [Box 4](#) on the Statutes of CESSDA).

Box 4: Service Providers' commitments under CESSDA's Statutes

The Statutes of CESSDA outline the key responsibilities of SPs, including upholding best practices as trustworthy data repositories. The Statutes are fundamental guidelines for maintaining CESSDA membership and ensuring high standards of data management. The Statutes are regularly reviewed and updated to strengthen SPs' contributions to the Consortium's mission.

While ESFRI KPIs monitor operational and scientific outputs, they do not explicitly integrate community principles such as FAIR, TRUST, and CARE, which are crucial for social science data repositories and research infrastructures. To address this gap, CESSDA has tailored its KPIs to align with the values of community-driven principles and address the needs of data archives. Looking ahead, integrating community principles into KPI frameworks can ensure that research infrastructures and data repositories not only meet performance benchmarks, but also promote transparency, responsible data management, and inclusive governance in the social science data ecosystem.

FAIR assessments

The FAIR principles provide a framework for ensuring that data are well-managed and useful for the research community. CESSDA SPs are a strong example of applying the FAIR principles. They perform particularly well in the *Findable* and *Accessible* aspects by making data easy to discover and retrieve.

To further advance FAIRness, CESSDA is actively improving machine-actionable features to enhance *Interoperability* and *Reusability*. For instance, the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) embeds metadata in JSON-LD/RDF format so that automated tools, e.g., [F-UJI](#), can evaluate FAIR compliance (see [Figure 2](#) for an example). Bulk assessments of the CDC metadata have demonstrated relatively high FAIR scores (Shepherdson and Papagiannopoulos, 2022). These assessments illustrate progress while highlighting areas for further improvement.

Moreover, several EC-funded projects are advancing FAIRness for research data. They include:

- [OSTrails](#) aims to deliver discipline-specific FAIR metrics, set minimum standards for digital objects, and establish APIs for exchanging FAIR assessment metrics.
- [FAIR Impact](#) is developing tools and metrics, including those specific to social sciences.

◆ Figure 2 An example of FAIR assessment result from the F-UJI tool

Assessment Results:

Evaluated Resource:

Save ↓ (JSON) New

FAIR level: moderate

Resource PID/URL: 10.5[redacted]

DataCite support: enabled

Metric Version: metrics_v0.5

Metric Specification: [https://doi.org/10.5\[redacted\]](https://doi.org/10.5[redacted])

Software version: 3.4.0

Download assessment results: [\(JSON\)](#)

Save and share assessment results:

Summary:

Source: Authors' illustration.

Key takeaways for funders, research infrastructures, data repositories, and researchers

Fostering community principles and openness in the social sciences and data ecosystems can have a great societal impact. However, quantifying their impact on society and research remains a difficult task. Moving forward, funders, research infrastructures, data repositories, and researchers can take actions to strengthen collaboration, leverage expertise, assess impact, and clarify standards to support open data.

For funders

National research funding agencies and the European Commission shape open science by promoting best practices and funding sustainable data access. They also encourage collaboration among research infrastructures, data repositories, researchers, and other funders to maximise the societal impact of open data.

1. **Encourage multi-disciplinary research and open data advocacy:** Promote and fund partnerships between researchers from different disciplines and policy actors to maximise data utility.
2. **Encourage the adoption of best practices through funding conditions:** Ensure funding conditions and Horizon Europe projects align with open science and community principles (i.e., TRUST, FAIR, and CARE). This will ensure funded projects adhere to best practices.
3. **Support trust-related initiatives:** Invest in projects that enhance transparency, accountability, and interoperability across national data repositories and research infrastructures in Europe.
4. **Expand support for long-term data preservation:** Invest in projects and training to enable a sustainable preservation system, which entails the retention, curation, and active long-term preservation of digital objects.

For research infrastructures

"Research infrastructures are facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructure, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation." (ESFRI, 2013)

1. **Engage with EOSC developments:** Maintain close engagement with EOSC developments, especially its Federation and Nodes. Facilitate knowledge exchange and network participation to ensure timely and adequate responses to relevant developments.
2. **Leverage trust-related outcomes:** Integrate findings from EU projects and RDA initiatives into operational strategies to harmonise practices and strengthen trust in research infrastructures.
3. **Promote TDR certification and FAIR practices:** Advocate for and support the adoption of TDR certification and FAIR principles to promote interdisciplinary and international collaboration.
4. **Advocate for interoperable technical services:** Promote transparency among TRSPs by encouraging the publication of service catalogues to facilitate repository service selection.
5. **Demonstrate impact and value-added:** Develop communication strategies to showcase the impact and value-added by research infrastructures, including dedicated web pages, narrative stories, and visualisations.
6. **Contribute to developing standards and tools for FAIR assessments:** Engage in the development of domain-specific FAIR assessment tools to align with community principles.

For data repositories

Data repositories (or data archives) serve as trusted platforms for storing, curating, and providing access to research data. They ensure compliance with best practices and long-term data preservation.

1. **Set standards for preservation and other repository operations:** Contribute to defining TDRs and building consensus on curation and preservation levels.
2. **Leverage domain-specific expertise in long-term data preservation:** Advocate for domain-specific services, such as data curation and metadata creation, and the benefits of long-term data preservation for future research and society.
3. **Increase visibility through registration:** Register in relevant registries and include repository identifiers on websites for broader dissemination.
4. **Explore innovative use of PIDs:** Expand the use of PIDs to cover datasets, studies, authors, data contributors, funders, and study components while standardising machine-readable metadata across repositories.
5. **Demonstrate public commitment to community principles:** Make public commitments to FAIR, TRUST, and CARE principles on websites and research outputs to build credibility and confidence with stakeholders.

For researchers

Researchers may work at universities, research institutes, data repositories, or research infrastructures. They generate, manage, and analyse data. They often engage with open science initiatives and advocate for best practices in data sharing and preservation.

1. **Advocate for open data and community principles:** Conduct and promote research on open data, open science frameworks, and their societal impact, particularly in the social sciences.
2. **Conduct multi-disciplinary research:** Collaborate with researchers across disciplines and engage in partnerships with policy actors to enhance data utility and societal benefits.
3. **Ensure compliance with open science policies:** Align research practices with evolving standards and funding agency requirements to improve adherence to open science policies.
4. **Utilise and contribute to FAIR assessment tools:** Participate in the development and refinement of FAIR assessment tools to enhance usability and effectiveness within specific domains.
5. **Expand the use of PIDs for research outputs:** Utilise persistent identifiers for individual study components to improve research discoverability and interoperability.

Closing remarks

This brief marks the first publicly available brief on CESSDA's efforts in advancing FAIR, TRUST, and CARE principles in the research infrastructure landscape. Through years of monitoring and collaboration with partners, CESSDA highlights key strategies to foster trust and openness in social science data archiving.

By engaging with ongoing EOSC developments, promoting certification, advocating for interoperable services, and advancing FAIR data compliance, CESSDA aims to strengthen collaborations with partners and alignment across research infrastructures. These actions are crucial for strengthening long-term data preservation and supporting interdisciplinary and international research. Although AI and other technological advancements are pertinent to data repositories, they have not been investigated in this brief. Exploring how technology and AI can leverage community principles and open data processes could be a promising area for future research.

By sharing these findings with a wider audience, CESSDA hopes to stimulate further discussions and investment in trustworthy data stewardship. CESSDA is committed to building a sustainable digital future – with a more open, collaborative, and impactful research ecosystem – that benefits the research community and society at large.

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